

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№12
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 920 sahifa,
2-dekabr, 2025-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijranovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Doniyorov S. M. – "Yangi O'zbekiston" va "Pravda Vostoka" gazetalarini tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the Editorial Board of the newspapers "Yangi Uzbekiston" and "Pravda Vostoka", Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Candidate of Philological Sciences (PhD)

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi” jurnali O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Yangi O'zbekiston sharoitida ayollar ijtimoiy faolligini oshirishda psixologik motivatsiya va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish strategiyalari	26
Xuseynova Abira Amanovna	
Pragmalinguodidactic Principles in Teaching English for Philologist Students and their Application in Intercultural Communication.....	31
Arzieva Bibi-Sanem Aynazarovna	
Metakognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan biologiya o'quv materiallarini loyihalash, joriy etish va samaradorligini baholash.....	35
Abdurasulova Gulrux Habibullayevna	
Oligofreniya holatida neyropsixologik tashxislar qo'llanilishining umumiy masalalari	40
Akramov Dostonbek Ikromjon o'g'li, Xojaliyeva Sarvinoz Elyorjon qizi	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarida kreativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida ...	44
Asatova Dildora Aslamovna	
Ingliz tili o'qish ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirishda autentik manbalarning roli.....	49
Bekmuratova Nargiza Arislanbayevna	
Insuldan keyingi nutqni tiklashda logopedik reabilitatsiya va nevrologik muolajalar integratsiyasi	52
Boltaboyeva Xurshida Sharofiddinovna	
The Concept of Symbols in Linguoculturology	56
Hamraqulova Gulandom Sodiq qizi	
Buyuk ipak yo'li xalqlari o'rtasidagi pedagogik va madaniy aloqalarning vujudga kelishi.....	59
Mirxalilova Nargiza Akbarovna	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni bolalarni nutqini o'stirishga bo'lgan kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorgarligini o'stirish	63
Mitaliboyeva Dildora	
Koxlear implantli bolalarning eshituv–nutqiy faolligini oshirishda differensial yondashuv asosida korreksion-pedagogik ish	66
Nartayeva Shahoza Yulchibayevna	
Fasilitatsion yondashuv asosida kichik maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda adaptiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishning psixologik-pedagogik mexanizmlari.....	71
Normatova Nilufar Komilovna	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda disgrafiyasi bo'lgan o'quvchilarda yozish kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari (XIX–XXI asrlarda).....	76
Qaxxorova Saidaxon, Mamarajabova Zulfiya	
Raqamli texnologiyalar va onlayn platformalar orqali olimpiya ta'limini rivojlantirish: yoshlar orasida axloqiy va jismoniy madaniyatni oshirish	80
Qodirov Jurabek Mamatsimonovich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida sun'iy intellekt bilim va savodxonligini rivojlantiradigan innovatsion jismoniy-interaktiv o'yinlar: pedagogik model.....	83
Quvonova Nodirabegim Shavkat qizi	
“Sab' ai sayyor” asarida qo'llangan onomastik birliklar haqida mulohazalar	87
Gadayev Oybek Yaxshiboyevich, Ravshanova Sharbatoy Rahmatilla qizi	
Ijtimoiy tarmoq shifokorlarining masofaviy konsultatsiyalari shaxs psixikasi va salomatligiga ta'siri	91
Askarova Nargiza Abdivaliyevna, Ravshanova Zarnigor Daminovna	
Talabalar ilmiy dunyoqarashini rivojlantirishda innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari va interfaol metodlardan foydalanish.....	95
Satvoldiyev Faxriddin Akbarali o'g'li	
Innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari orqali pedagoglarning kreativligini rivojlantirish	99
Saydullayeva Gulasal Umidjon qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar motorikasini rivojlantirishning standart modeli	102
Sirojiddinova Xamidaxon Xasanboy qizi	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning shaxslararo munosabat kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	106
Turg'unova Gulnoza Muhammadjonovna, Xodjiyeva Mahliyo	

Shaxsdagi mehnat motivatsiyasi samaradorligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiluvchi korrelyatsion bog'liqliklar tahlili	109
Xusanov Samariddin Maxmadaminovich	
Auditoriyadan tashqari musiqiy mashg'ulotlarni art-terapiya yordamida tashkil etish asoslari	112
Yarashev Jo'rabek To'rayevich	
Формирование творческого мышления школьников на уроках музыки	117
Габдульманова Ильнура Минисламовна	
Теоретико-методологические основы коллаборативного обучения, кооперативных подходов и интерактивных педагогических методов	119
Жураева Мафтуна Бахтиёр кизи	
Педагогическое колесо как инструмент формирования цифровой компетентности будущих педагогов дошкольного образования.....	124
Урзова М. Б., Усманова У. Б.	
Особенности гражданского воспитания обучающихся в системе “школа–махалла” в Узбекистане ..	130
Хайдаров Шавкат Шамсиддин угли	
Педагогические условия формирования языковой грамотности у учащихся с тяжелыми нарушениями речи.....	135
Юсупова Зулайхо Бахром кизи	
Valeologik tarbiyada o'yin texnologiyalarining ahamiyati.....	139
Berkinova Charos Islomovna	
O'quvchilarda faol fuqarolik kompetensiyasi tushunchasi, mazmuni va shakllanishi	142
Buvorayeva Gulruh Shoikrom qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda STEAM yondashuvi asosida o'qitishning didaktik imkoniyatlari	145
Cho'tboyeva Munisxon Eshpo'lat qizi	
Tabiatga muhabbat: maktabgacha ta'limda milliy qadriyatlar va o'yinlar orqali ekologik tarbiya	150
Ergasheva Umriniso Komilovna	
Zamonaviy ta'lim – talabalar ijtimoiy intellektini shakllantirish omilidir.....	153
Ermatova Gulnoz Pirimovna	
O'zbekistonning eng yangi tarixi fanini o'qitishda pedagogik texnologiyaning o'rni	156
Gazibekova Feruza Hakimovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining raqamli texnologiyalar muhitida tanqidiy va mustaqil fikrlashini rivojlantirish metodikasi	159
Haydarova Feruza Haydar qizi	
Talabalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy fazilatlar va sifatlarni shakllantirish mexanizmi.....	162
Jumanazarova Dilnoza Umurzaqovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning kasbga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini shakllantirishda interfaol metodlarni qo'llash texnologiyasi.....	165
Jumayeva Malika Aliyevna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarda kasbiy-nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish.....	168
Lutfetdinova Ra'no Xusnetdinovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda matematik rivojlanishga zamonaviy yondashuvlar va jahon tajribalari ..	172
Masharipova Barno Erkin qizi, Adilbayeva Dilnoza Adilbay qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida til o'yinlari texnologiyalarining nazariy asoslari.....	175
Masharipova Dilfuza Muxammatjon qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachisi pedagogik faoliyatining o'ziga xosligi	178
Muhammadiyeva Feruza Turakulovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini og'zaki va yozma nutqini rivojlantirishda aksiologik yondashuvdan foydalanish metodikasi.....	181
Muhiddinova Munira Xayrullayevna	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida matematika fanini o'qitishda raqamli transformatsiya vositalaridan foydalanishning metodik paradigmasi	184
Narzullayeva Sevara Omonovna	
O'qituvchining muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	187
Nizamova Nodira Paxritdinovna	
Integrativ yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarning nutqiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning mazmuniy izohlanishi	191
Oysha Qurbonova, Nodira Abduraimova	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda Finlandiya tajribasi	195
Nodira Sherboyeva	

Kutubxonachi kutubxona-axborot xizmati jarayonining yetakchi ishtirokchisi sifatida	198
O'ktam Nosirov	
Pedagogik ta'lim transformatsiyasida talabalarning tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi.....	204
Rustamova Shoxista Omonjonovna	
Globallashuv sharoitida axborot-psixologik xavfsizlikni shakllantirish masalalari.....	208
Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li	
Talabalarga ingliz tilini o'qitishning zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalari	212
Sa'dullayeva Rushana	
Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	215
Saidova Dilbar Erkinovna	
Pedagog xodimlarda tolerantlik namoyon bo'lishining determinantlari.....	218
Sattorova Maxliyo Dilmurod qizi	
Kreativ metodlar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kreativ tafakkur va fikrlashni rivojlantirish	223
Sultonboyeva Baxriniso Ilhomjon qizi	
Artpedagogika texnologiyalaridan foydalanib maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda dialogik nutqni rivojlantirish metodikasi	226
Xolmatova Fotima Baxtiyor qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda yashil kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish yo'nalishlari.....	229
Yaqubova Shoira Tog'aymuratovna	
Emotsional intellektni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	233
Yarmatov Raxmboy Baxramovich	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'quv veb-saytlari orqali til kompetentligini rivojlantirish	239
Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna, Muxammadjonova Diyorabonu Muzaffarjon qizi	
Языковые изменения в русском языке XXI века: исследование новых слов, сленга, интернет-коммуникации, влияния англицизмов и глобализации на современный русский язык	242
Марупова Дилфуза Давроновна	
Oliy ta'limda talabalarning ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyatining maqsad va vazifalari	247
F. R. Xosilova	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim texnologiya darslarida o'quvchilarni tabiiy materiallar bilan ishlashga o'rgatish	251
Kambarov Nodirjon Sattarovich, Nasirjanova Feruzaxon Alixon qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda STEAM yondashuvining qo'llanilishi va uning samaradorligi.....	256
Abdulazizova Yulduz Abdujabbor qizi	
Tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishda STEAM yondashuvi asosida kreativlikni rivojlantirish metodikasi	259
Abdullayeva Dilrabo Fayzulla qizi	
Umumta'lim maktablarida o'quvchilarda shaxs ma'naviy qiyofasini shakllantirishning zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalari.....	262
Aliyeva Zuxra Tursunboyevna	
Yosh avlodni madaniy-tarixiy yondashuv asosida tarbiyalashda madaniy-ma'rifiy muassasalarning o'rni..	265
Aripov Shokirjon Olimovich	
Ta'limda yangi texnologiya: 4K modeli va uni amalga oshirish yo'llari.....	268
Avliyoqulova Nasiba Choriyevna	
Badiiy-tarixiy materiallarni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiyalashning metodologik asoslari.....	272
Baratov Baxtiyorjon Qodirovich	
Bolaning maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotiga moslashishida o'yinning roli.....	275
Barno Masharipova Erkin qizi, Zuhrobova Mahliyo Abdulatif qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish savodxonligi darslarida integrativ yondoshuvdan foydalanish texnologiyasi	278
Ernazarova Laylo Abdusaitovna, Saidahmadova Gulrux Farrux qizi	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda metarefleksiv fikrlashni rivojlantirishning psixologik-pedagogik asoslari	284
Ismailova Nilufar Isroildjanovna	
Semantic and Cross-Cultural Features of Food-Based Idioms in Karakalpak and English Languages.....	289
Jiemuratova Gulistan Koshkinbaevna	
Filolog talabalarida mustaqil fikrlash va qaror qabul qilishni rivojlantirishda metakognitiv yondashuvlarning didaktik mexanizmlari.....	292
Jo'rayeva Dilnoza Ro'zimat qizi	
Rivojlantiruvchi sohalar kompetensiyalariga integratsion yondashuv asosida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalash texnologiyasini rivojlantirish	296
Jo'rayeva Zilola Sayfiddin qizi	

Psixologlar kasbiy komponentlarini rivojlantirishda matematik usullardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	302
<i>Kuziyeva Dilnura Dilmurotovna</i>	
O'zbekiston metodik maktabida sotsiolingvistik kompetensiyani shakllantirish bo'yicha olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar tahlili	306
<i>Madaminova Gulzira Gulamkadirovna</i>	
Maxsus pedagogika fanlarini o'qitishning nazariy-metodik asoslari	313
<i>Maqsudova Nodira Alijonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda metakognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishda ertakterapiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish metodikasi	317
<i>Muxiddinova Dilfuza Sherdor qizi</i>	
Nutq madaniyatini shakllantirishda o'qituvchi nutqining roli.....	320
<i>N. Q. Olimova</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida matematika fanini o'qitishda raqamli transformatsiya vositalaridan foydalanishning metodik paradigmasi	323
<i>Narzullayeva Sevara Omonovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda ekologik madaniyatni shakllantirish metodikasi	326
<i>Normirzayeva Maftunaxon Ilyosjon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tadqiqot faoliyatini rivojlantirishda intensiv ta'lim texnologiyalarining metodik asoslari.....	329
<i>Oloqulova Farzona Umedillayevna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi giperaktiv bolalar bilan ishlashda pedagogik kompetentligini oshirish metodikasi.....	332
<i>Raimqulova Sojida Abdusaid qizi</i>	
Talabalarning tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari	335
<i>Rustamova Shoxista Omonjonovna</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etishning xorijiy pedagogik amaliyotdagi modellari	339
<i>Sultonova Zarina Uchqun qizi</i>	
Xalq pedagogikasida ertaklarning tarbiyaviy va ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ahamiyati: ma'naviy begonlashuvga qarshi tarbiyaviy omil sifatida.....	343
<i>To'xtasinova Farida Davlatali qizi</i>	
B1 darajadagi talabalar uchun xorijiy tilni o'qitishda audiovizual texnologiyalar yordamida ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishning metodik asoslari	347
<i>Toshpulatova Shaxsanam Xolmurodovna</i>	
Kontekstli ta'lim va uning boshlang'ich ta'lim matematikasidagi ahamiyati haqida	350
<i>Umarova Nigora Alisherovna</i>	
Oiladagi psixologik muhitning o'spirinlarda to'liqsizlik kompleksi shakllanishiga ta'siri	353
<i>Xalmuratova Dilorom Abdikarimovna</i>	
Ta'limda faktcheking: misinformatsiya va dizinformatsiyaga qarshi kurashishning pedagogik asoslari	356
<i>Xidirova Maftuna Ithom qizi</i>	
Maktab o'quvchilarini falsafiy va dunyoqarashga tayyorlash omillari	362
<i>Xo'shboqova Farida Komiljon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida nutq faoliyatini rivojlantirishning lingokognitiv asoslari	370
<i>Xusanova Gulruxsor To'lqin qizi, Aliyeva Muhlis Baxodir qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyasini oshirish	374
<i>Zokirova Sohobaxon Muxtaraliyevna, Erkinova Nazokatxon Anvarjon qizi</i>	
Эффективность занятий кроссфитом в повышении уровня общей физической подготовленности слушателей института повышения квалификации МВД Республики Узбекистан	377
<i>Албеков Шокир Адилбекович</i>	
Роль торговых и кочевых маршрутов в формировании лингвокультурных заимствований между Хорезмом и Южной Сибирью.....	381
<i>Сатымова Светлана Сатымовна</i>	
Использование искусственного интеллекта в обучении русскому языку как иностранному: проблемы и решения.....	385
<i>Ташева Дилором Салимовна</i>	
Проблемы использования коммуникативного метода в преподавании русского языка студентам	389
<i>Тоджибоева Наргиза Джумабоевна</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

Maktab–oila–mahalla hamkorligining qizlar ijtimoiy faolligini oshirishga ta'siri	393
<i>Abdurazoqova Marg'uba Muxammad qizi</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida musiqiy madaniyatni takomillashtirishning metodologik imkoniyatlari.....	397
<i>Asqarova Xurshida A'zamjon qizi</i>	
Maktab biologiya kursini o'qitishda dars va darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarning o'zaro bog'liqligi asosida metodologik savodxonlikni shakllantirish.....	404
<i>Azimov Bekjon Ibrohimjon o'g'li</i>	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida iqtidorli talabalar bilan ishlash samaradorligini ta'minlash usullari.....	407
<i>Delov To'liqin Erkinovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarni badiiy asarlarni janriy xususiyatlariga ko'ra izohli o'qishga o'rgatish	410
<i>Gulmira Abdullayeva</i>	
O'zbekiston bokschilarining dunyo reytingida yetakchi o'rinlarni egallashining asosiy omillari	413
<i>Insapov Ismoil Tuychaliyevich</i>	
Improving Learners' Engagement Through Game-Based Techniques in Language Education	416
<i>Ismailova Ma'rifat Bakhrambek kizi</i>	
STEAM yondashuvi boshlang'ich ta'limda ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning zamonaviy kaliti sifatida	421
<i>Jo'rayeva Nasiba Komil qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarni milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyalashning ijtimoiylashuvi	426
<i>Jo'rayeva Sayyora Vahobjon qizi</i>	
O'smirlarda xarakter aksentuatsiyasining o'ziga bo'lgan ishonch rivojlanishiga ta'sirining psixologik xususiyatlari	429
<i>Jurayev Xaydarjon Odilboyevich</i>	
O'spirinlarda agressiv xulqqa ta'sir qiluvchi omillar	433
<i>Konratbayeva Ayjamal Bazarbayevna</i>	
Rus va o'zbek tillarida chorvachilik terminlarining qiyosiy tahlili.....	436
<i>Kurbanova Guzal Abduraximovna</i>	
Texnologiya darslarida murakkab mexanizmlarni o'qitishning zamonaviy usullari	441
<i>Mamadaliyev Furqat Xolmamatovich</i>	
Umumta'lim maktab o'qituvchilarining sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish madaniyatini shakllantirish usullari	446
<i>Mamatova Fazilat Ixtiyorovna, Xolmirzayeva Zebo Ravshan qizi</i>	
Nutqda badiiy tasviriy vositalardan foydalanish yo'llari.....	450
<i>Murodova Farangis G'anisherovna</i>	
Kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarning yozma savodxonligini oshirish yo'llari.....	454
<i>N. Abduvaliyeva, M. Odinajonova</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar shaxslararo munosabatini korreksiyalashda ertak terapiyasidan foydalanish	458
<i>Nig'matova Nodirabegim Lutfillo qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	463
<i>O'rinova Ro'zigul Jumanazar qizi</i>	
Voleybol o'yinida blok qo'yish texnikasini o'rgatishda yangi pedagogik yondashuvlar	467
<i>Qambarov Kozimjon</i>	
Texnik yo'nalishda tahsil olayotgan talabalarga ingliz tilini o'qitishning yangi texnologiyalari	472
<i>Babayeva Gulnozaxon Latibjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim sifatini oshirishda pedagog malakasining roli	481
<i>Davlatova Dildora Nuriddinovna</i>	
Talabalarda sog'lom turmush tarzini rivojlantirishning pedagogik tamoyillari	485
<i>Davronov Nurzod Ismoilovich</i>	
Eshitishda nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar: toifalari va tasniflash mezonlari	490
<i>Djurayeva Sohiba Barat qizi</i>	
Blum taksonomiyasiga asoslanib boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining og'zaki va yozma nutqini rivojlantirish usullari.....	495
<i>Husenova Aziza Sharipovna</i>	
Tabiiy fan darslari jarayonida o'quvchilarda loyihaviy ishlarni tashkil etish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish	498
<i>Matniyazova Diyora Jumanazarovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limni modernizatsiya qilishning asosiy yo'nalishlari: innovatsion taraqqiyot, metodik yangiliklar va istiqbollari	501
<i>Nazarova Mohigul Akmalovna, Asatova Mashhura Asomiddin qizi</i>	

Kasbiy pedagogikani shakllantirish va rivojlantirish masalalari	506
<i>Sanaqulov Xamroqul Rizaqulovich</i>	
O'qituvchining shaxsiy fazilatlari va suggestiv kompetentligining o'zaro bog'liqligi	513
<i>Shermatova Manzura Ikromjanovna</i>	
Tez qalamchizgilarda innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llash tajribasi	518
<i>Suyunov Navro'z Alisher o'g'li</i>	
Kognitiv tilshunoslik asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqini rivojlantirish	523
<i>Teshabiyev Dilmurod Raxmadjonovich, Madazimova Muxlisa Abdurashid qizi</i>	
Kombinatorik masalalar asosida ijodiy topshiriqlarni tuzish va ularning o'quvchilarga ta'siri	526
<i>Toshboyeva Saida Rahmonberdiyevna, Yusupova Latofat Abduqodir qizi</i>	
Linguodidactic Foundations for Enhancing Professional Competence in Practice-Oriented Language Education	530
<i>Uktamova Navruza Botir qizi</i>	
Audiovizual usul qo'llanilganda o'quvchilarning til ko'nikmalaridagi o'zgarishlarni baholash	535
<i>Umarov Aziz Avazovich</i>	
Ona tili – ART texnologiya va kreativlik fanida so'z san'atining omili sifatida	540
<i>X. Sanaqulov, Sh. Nurmatova</i>	
Etnopedagogik yondashuvning boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijtimoiylashuv jarayoniga ta'siri	543
<i>Xamroqulova Xilola Qosimjon qizi</i>	
Ajdodlarimiz o'g'itlari asosida o'quvchi-yoshlarda axloqiy sifatlarni shakllantirish texnologiyasi	547
<i>Xatamova Nilufar Xaydarovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ o'qish madaniyatini rivojlantirishda generativ sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining didaktik imkoniyatlari	550
<i>Xayitova Firuza Abdullayevna</i>	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda maktabgacha ta'limning mazmuni va tarixiy taraqqiyoti	554
<i>Yoziyeva Umida Lutfullayevna</i>	
O'quv vaziyatlarini loyihalash orqali talabalar o'quv faolligini oshirish	558
<i>Zakirova Dilfuza Sayidolimovna</i>	
O'quvchilar orasida jismoniy faollikni oshirish uchun yangi ilmiy yondashuvlar	561
<i>Zaynobidinov Dilshodbek Qobilovich</i>	
Активные методы обучения как коммуникационная основа современного урока	566
<i>Ахмедова Мукаддас Ходиматовна</i>	
Инклюзия как путь к равным возможностям: развитие системы образования Узбекистана	570
<i>Баротова Шохсанам Бахтиёр кизи, Мауш Ребия Джамshedовна, Мурадова Дилфуза Махмудовна</i>	
“Qurilish konstruksiyalari” fanini o'qitishda kasbiy-amaliy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish	576
<i>No'manova Soxiba Ergashboyevna</i>	
Креативный педагогический подход в музыкально-теоретических и практических занятиях по искусству макома	582
<i>Нурматова Фируза Муминовна</i>	
Система упражнений по методике обучения средствам речевой выразительности узбекского языка	587
<i>Фаттахова Д. А.</i>	
Oliy ta'limda kompetensiyaga asoslangan o'qitish modellari	592
<i>Ernazarov Alisher Ergashevich, Chinqulova Gulmehra</i>	
The Concept of Symbols in Linguoculturology	598
<i>Hamraqulova Gulandom Sodiq qizi</i>	
Raqamli o'yinlarga (mobile games) qaramlikning kognitiv samaradorlikka salbiy ta'siri	601
<i>Turamov Muhammadzohid Rustamjon o'g'li</i>	
OTM talabalarini vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalash asosida ilmiy tadqiqot ishlariga yo'naltirishning zamonaviy metodlari	605
<i>Sobirov Zahriddin Sadriddinovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda o'quvchilarda kiriyativlikni rivojlantirish	609
<i>Qo'chqarov Mirzavali Qo'zibayevich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari tarbiyalanuvchilarining axloqiy tarbiyasini shakllantirish	613
<i>Yaqubova Dinora Bahodirovna</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida AR (Augmented Reality) texnologiyalarining qo'llanilishi	617
<i>Abdumo'minov Burxonjon Sunnatillo o'g'li</i>	

The Role of Psychological Support in the Formation of Students' Socio-Emotional Competence in Preschool Education	622
Kamol'dinova Diyora Jaloliddin qizi	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish metodikasi	626
Xudoynazarova Moxira Xakimovna	
Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalarda tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatini metodlar orqali rivojlantirish.....	629
Ro'zmetov Ravshan Sharipbayevich	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda muloqot madaniyatini tarbiyalash	633
Uljayeva Sevara Abdirazzoqovna	
Kompetensiyaviy yondashuvga asoslangan zamonaviy darsliklar tuzilishi va mazmuni.....	638
Po'latova Marjona Inomjon qizi	
STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasini maktabgacha ta'limida qo'llash bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar	643
Saidova Nigora Olimovna, Pirmatova Zaynabxon Elmurod qizi	
Raqamli texnologiyalar vositasida bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning pedagogik muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantirish	646
Ergasheva Sunbula Baxtiyor qizi	
O'quvchilarda ijtimoiy tarmoqlarga qaramlikning shakllanishi va uning dolzarb muammolari	650
Gapparova Mastona Safaraliyevna	
Adabiyot darslarini o'qitishda 5E modelidan foydalanish	654
Abdiraupova Zarnigor Abdinabi qizi	
Oliy ta'limda kompetensiyaga asoslangan o'qitish modellari.....	657
Ernazarov Alisher Ergashovich, Chinqulova Gulmehra	
Traditional Techniques and Modern Approaches in the Production of National Costumes	665
Jabborova Dilshoda Xolmamat qizi	
Pedagogik platformalar va kognitiv-didaktik yondashuvlar integratsiyasi yordamida talabalarning kasbiy tayyorgarlik tizimini yangi bosqichga olib chiqish.....	668
Raxmonov Omadjon Mamasidiq o'g'li	
Aqli zaif o'quvchilarda disgrafiyaning bartaraf etishda assistiv texnologiyalarning ahamiyati	672
Usmonov Umid Allayorovich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tayanch hayotiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish.....	676
Adizova Nigora Baxtiyorovna, Akbarova Sarvinoz Sadriiddinovna	
Tadqiqotchilik kompetentligi pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	681
Ergashev Nozim Nabiyevich	
Teaching Reading to Young Learners: Essential Principles for Primary School Teachers	684
Toshtanova Maftuna Xamidjon qizi	
Tarmoq qurilmalari va tizimlarini boshqarish modulini o'qitish orqali o'quvchilarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlash.....	687
Karimova Charos Abduhalim qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda og'zaki nutq rivojlanishining psixolingvistik asoslari	691
Musayeva Nafisa Kudratovna, Muxammadova Saodat Muzaffar qizi	
"Kasbiy ma'naviyat" fani bo'lajak pedagoglarda ma'naviy-axloqiy kompetensiyalarni intensiv rivojlantirish omili	695
Ismoilov Yoqubjon Quchqarboyevich	
Yapon tilini o'rgatishda talabalarning gapirish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirish: tamoyillar, bosqichlar va innovatsion usullar	699
Baqoyev Navro'zjon Abdullo o'g'li	
Texnologik ta'lim jarayonida ixtirochilik va loyihalashtirish kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	705
Zokirova Nargiza Akbarjonovna	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarda kasbiy kompetentlikni shakllantirishning psixologik asoslari.....	710
Eshnazarova Farida Jo'raqulovna	
Ta'lim islohotlari sharoitida genderni yo'naltirilgan ta'limni tashkil etishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	714
Yaxyayeva Sojida Abduraximovna	
Ko'rsatish olmoshlarining vazifaviy uslublarda qo'llanilishi.....	718
Berdiyeva Malika	
Nazorat turlari orqali o'quvchilarning savodxonlik kompensatsiyasini shakllantirish	721
Xoldarova Irodaxon Valijonovna, Jo'rayeva Shodiya Kenjaali qizi	

Zamonaviy boshlang'ich ta'limni modernizatsiya qilish sharoitida o'quvchilarda lug'atlar bilan ishlash kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	726
Buvajonova Mohiraxon Usmonali qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limni modernizatsiya qilishning asosiy yo'nalishlari: innovatsion taraqqiyot, metodik yangiliklar va istiqbollari	731
Nazarova Mohigul Akmalovna	
Maktab va pedagogika institutlari o'rtasida amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan dual ta'lim modelini takomillashtirish: muammolar va yechimlar	736
Arabova Muxiba Bazarovna	
Помощь советского государства в подготовке кадров для арабских государств	740
Хомидова Камола	
Место Узбекистана в развитии культурной сферы Советского союза во второй половине XX века ..	744
Бекназаров Собиржон	
Toshkent xalqaro kinofestivallarining Arab davlatlari va Afrika mamlakatlari kinosan'atida tutgan o'rni	748
Sharifov Shoxjaxon To'liqinjon o'g'li	
Ekonometrika fanini o'qitishda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning nazariy asoslari va istiqbollari	752
Bobonorova Qundizxon Quralbay qizi	
O'quvchi faolligini oshirishda jadid maktablari tajribasi va faol ta'lim metodlarining integrativ qo'llanilishi ..	759
Bobonazarov Orif Abrayqulovich	
Влияние гендерной лингвистики на развитие психолингвистических исследований в Узбекистане ..	764
Мусаева Елена Казимовна	
Psixik rivojlanishni tashxislashda psixofiziologik usullardan foydalanish samaradorligi	767
Sh. L. Rahmonova	
Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	770
Saidova Dilbar Erkinovna	
Ingliz tili o'qitishda integrativ (CLIL) texnologiyasining boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun mos modellarini ishlab chiqish	773
Xakimova Xosiyat Jurayevna	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlar ta'lim tizimida talabalarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish usullari	776
Mirzayeva Faroxat Odiljonovna, Odiljonova Shoxsanam Abdug'appon qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirishda innovatsion o'yin metodlarining ahamiyati	785
Ikromov Ilxom Muxamadrasimovich	
Tabiat tasvirining adabiy janrlarga ko'ra o'ziga xosliklari	790
Fozilova Mohigul Farxodovna	
Методические подходы к развитию прагматической компетентности старшеклассников на основе чтения аутентичных материалов	794
Исаматдинова Машхура Икромжон кизи	
O'zbek tilida "zahar" konseptining leksik-semantik va pragmatik xususiyatlari	799
Shokirov Sherhali Ibrohimovich, Baxramov Xabibillo Sadikovich	
Integrativ modulli o'qitish tizimi samaradorligining miqdoriy va sifat tahlili	803
Nurmanova Nazira	
Sog'lom turmush tarzi ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda STEAM ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati	807
Toshova Shaxnoza Tojidorovna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga harakatga doir masalalarni klaster metodida o'rgatish	811
Badalov Dilmurod Abdixalilovich	
Ona tili darslarida o'quv lug'atlaridan foydalanishning o'quvchilarning og'zaki nutq kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi didaktik asoslari	817
Ahmedova Adiba Ulug'bek qizi	
Philosophical Aspects and Analysis of the Regularities of the Formation of Geo-Economic Thinking	822
Ubaydullayev Islomjon Abdullayevich	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarini sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanishga tayyorlashning pedagogik asoslari	826
Xudayqulova Fazilat Bo'riyevna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

Boshlang'ich ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonida o'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini shakllantirishda ommaviy axborot vositalarining (Media/Mass Communication) roli.....	831
Bo'ronova Dilrabo Ne'matullayevna	
Inkluziv maktab sharoitida kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-perseptiv tajribani shakllantirish	835
Karimova Zulfiya Abduraxmanovna	
TEACCH konsepsiyasi – autizm va kommunikativ buzilishlari bo'lgan bolalarni davolash va o'qitish dasturi.....	839
Murodova Sarvigul Raxim qizi	
Модернизация кадровой политики дошкольных учреждений через инновационные мониторинговые механизмы	843
Ким Нигора Каримовна	
Bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarining metodik kompetentligini ergonomik yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish	847
Usmonova Xafiza	
Pedagogik improvizatsiya asosida talabalar o'quv faoliyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik strategiyalari	852
Ergasheva Muhayyoxon G'anijonovna	
Talabalar orasida ilmiy-pedagogik tadqiqotlarni tashkil etish va o'tkazish	857
Nurmatova Madina Odiljon qizi, Qo'shoqova Farangiz Azizbek qizi	
O'quvchi-yoshlarni oilaga nisbatan ma'naviy-axloqiy va qadriyatli munosabatlarga tayyorlash – ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyat sifatida	861
Xaydarov Oxunjon Murodjonovich	
Talabalarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda mustaqil ta'limning ilmiy-metodik ahamiyati	866
B. Normamatova	
Talabalarda pedagogik e'tiqodni shakllantirishning variativ modeli va uning asosiy komponentlari	869
Bahranova Hulkar Bahran qizi	
Konvensial yondashuv asosida talabalarni mustaqil ta'lim olish samaradorligining didaktik imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirish.....	872
Berdiyev Bahodir Ravshanovich	
Kontekstli yondashuvga asoslangan o'quv-ijodiy faoliyatning turlari	875
Botirova Zilola Nodirovna	
Raqamli texnologiyalar vositasida bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning pedagogik muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantirish.....	878
Ergasheva Sunbula Baxtiyor qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinflarida ta'lim o'quvchilarga sonlar haqida ma'lumot berish	882
Hakimova Zulfizar Umrzoq qizi	
Biologiya ta'limida elektron ta'lim (E-Learning) va aralash ta'lim (Blended Learning) texnologiyalarining samaradorligini tahlil qilish.....	886
Kozimov Akbarjon A'zamjon o'g'li	
Alisher Navoiy asarlarida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyaga oid fikrlari tahlili.....	891
M. Ibragimova	
Integratsiyalashgan dars ta'limiy faoliyat samaradaorligini ta'minlovchi muhim omil sifatida	894
Mahmatqulova Xosiyat Bobomurod qizi	
Tarbiyalanuvchilarni xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalari asosida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalashning mazmunini ochib berish.....	897
Murodillayeva Durdona Dilmurodovna	
Sun'iy intellekt davrida bolalar adabiyoti: raqamli qahramonlar, interaktiv ertaklar va bolaning ijodiy tafakkuri rivoji	900
Normurodova Nigora Abdusattorovna, Sharipova Iroda Rashid qizi	
Qadimgi va o'rta asr mutafakkirlarining matematika fanining shakllanishi va rivojlanishidagi o'rni	903
Quvvatova Ozoda Gulbek qizi	
Shaxs xolistik rivojlanishi – psixologik-pedagogik muammo sifatida	906
Rashidova Xurriyat Sulaymonovna	
Bolalarda elementar matematik tasavvurlarni shakllantirishning psixologik-pedagogik asoslari.....	908
Ravshanova Kamola Toxirovna	
Matematikaga rivojiga ulkan hissa qo'shgan olimlar	911
To'rayeva Kamola Vosidjon qizi	

Umumiy o'rta ta'limda mexanika masalalarini yechish metodikasi va o'qitish jarayonining didaktik asoslari	914
Toxirova Maxfuzaxon Otaqo'ziyevna	
Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachi-pedagogalarining kasbiy-axloqiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish	916
Xabibullayeva Sayyoraxon Maxamadali qizi	

PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS AND ANALYSIS OF THE REGULARITIES OF THE FORMATION OF GEO- ECONOMIC THINKING

Ubaydullayev Islomjon Abdullayevich

PhD, Associate Professor of the Department
of Social Sciences of UBS

Abstract: The article is devoted to a philosophical analysis of the regularities in the formation of geo-economic thinking. It examines the dialectical development of geo-economic thinking, its historical and epistemological foundations, as well as the mechanisms of transformation in relation to economic space. Within the context of global relations, the study analyzes value shifts in geo-economic thinking and their impact on societal development. The author proposes theoretical and methodological foundations that can be practically applied in the development of geo-economic policies, regional development strategies, and the management of global economic relations.

Key words: geo-economic thinking, society, social philosophy, world economy, globalization processes, economic thinking, economic culture, property-owning class, geo-economic thinking of property owners, geo-economic concepts, ontological and epistemological foundations, philosophical analysis, dialectics, economic space, global relations, regional development.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada geoiqtisodiy tafakkurning shakllanish qonuniyatlari falsafiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Unda geoiqtisodiy tafakkurning dialektik rivojlanishi, uning tarixiy va gnoseologik asoslari hamda iqtisodiy fazo bilan bog'liq holda yuzaga keladigan o'zgarish mexanizmlari yoritiladi. Global munosabatlar kontekstida geoiqtisodiy tafakkurdagi qiymatliy siljishlar va ularning jamiyat taraqqiyotiga ta'siri tahlil etiladi. Shuningdek, geoiqtisodiy siyosatni ishlab chiqish, mintaqaviy rivojlanish strategiyalarini shakllantirish va global iqtisodiy munosabatlarni boshqarishda amaliy qo'llash mumkin bo'lgan nazariy-metodologik asoslar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: geoiqtisodiy tafakkur, jamiyat, ijtimoiy falsafa, jahon iqtisodiyoti, globallashuv jarayonlari, iqtisodiy tafakkur, iqtisodiy madaniyat, mulkdorlar sinfi, mulkdorlarning geoiqtisodiy tafakkuri, geoiqtisodiy tushunchalar, ontologik va gnoseologik asoslar, falsafiy tahlil, dialektika, iqtisodiy fazo, global munosabatlar, mintaqaviy rivojlanish.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена философскому анализу закономерностей формирования геоэкономического мышления. В ней рассматриваются диалектическое развитие геоэкономического мышления, его исторические и гносеологические основания, а также механизмы изменений в связи с экономическим пространством. В контексте глобальных отношений анализируются ценностные сдвиги в геоэкономическом мышлении и их влияние на развитие общества. Автор предлагает теоретико-методологические основы, которые могут быть практически использованы при разработке геоэкономической политики, стратегий регионального развития и управлении глобальными экономическими отношениями.

Ключевые слова: геоэкономическое мышление, общество, социальная философия, мировая экономика, процессы глобализации, экономическое мышление, экономическая культура, класс собственников, геоэкономическое мышление собственников, геоэкономические концепции, онтологические и гносеологические основы, философский анализ, диалектика, экономическое пространство, глобальные отношения, региональное развитие.

INTRODUCTION

Geo-economic processes in the world economy require each owner to quickly comprehend the logic of their development and to create their own system of trade turnover relations. The notion of the geo-economic logic of the development of processes is realized through a geo-economic way of thinking.

Thus, if a social entity consists of a set of processes and events designed to meet the needs of people and created through their practical activity, social consciousness represents a reflection of natural and social reality, encompassing a complex of sensations, feelings, opinions, ideas, and theories characteristic of a specific period of societal development. Since social consciousness can be divided into several forms based on the reflection of social events and processes, it includes economic, political, moral, legal, aesthetic, environmental, and other dimensions.

Taking the methodological characteristics of social philosophy and the subject of consciousness as a theoretical basis, it is possible to formulate the following definition of economic consciousness. Economic consciousness, as a form of social consciousness, represents a unified system of theories and ideas, attitudes, ideals, perceptions, sensations, and emotional experiences aimed at awareness, comprehension, and transformation of the future economic and spiritual life of modern society, particularly the economic relations that arise between individuals.

This definition also demonstrates that economic consciousness integrates elements of emotional and rational cognition. Within this system, economic thinking occupies a special and distinctive place.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Russian scientist L. N. Ponomarev and Uzbek scientist B. Valiev provide the following definition of the concept of economic thinking: "From the point of view of philosophy, economic thinking is the main form of reflection of economic events, corresponding knowledge, and the generalization of significant links in economic relations, as well as the generation of new ideas and awareness of the trends in economic events and processes. This reflects economic relations and events in such forms of thought as ideas, concepts, judgments, and conclusions. It represents the advancement and development of thought associated with the formation of specific economic ideas, knowledge, views, and attitudes toward economic reality" [1: 2; 4].

Based on this approach and the assumption that economic thinking applies to the comprehension of various aspects of economic processes, it can be classified into macroeconomic thinking, microeconomic thinking, national economic thinking, geo-economic thinking, geo-financial thinking, ethno-economic thinking, external economic thinking, and other forms.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this article is based on qualitative and theoretical approaches. Data were obtained through a systematic review of philosophical, economic, and geo-economic scholarly sources, including classical and contemporary scientific literature, academic journals, and monographs relevant to geo-economic thinking and globalization processes. The study also relies on conceptual analysis of key philosophical categories such as economic consciousness, economic space, and globalization. The collected materials were analyzed using dialectical and comparative methods, which made it possible to identify regularities, internal connections, and value shifts in the formation of geo-economic thinking. Logical analysis and synthesis were applied to generalize theoretical positions and to reveal the ontological and epistemological foundations of geo-economic thinking in the context of global economic relations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Geo-economic thinking is one of the forms of economic thinking, representing a dialectical reflection of such forms of thought as notions, judgments, and conclusions, expressed through ideas, ideals, attitudes, thoughts, and actions that take place within the geo-economic space of economic, political, legal, and spiritual processes involving all actors engaged in economic relations in the world market. In particular, it represents a system of modern mental activity that embodies theoretical and practical knowledge, experience, and skills acquired for generating profit based on an understanding of trends in the process of trade turnover.

The process of formation of geo-economic thinking incorporates two main features.

The first feature is associated with the task of forming geo-economic thinking within individual consciousness and includes two complementary directions. On the one hand, at the empirical level, it involves perception through direct observation of ongoing economic relations between states and economic processes taking place in the world. On the other hand, it encompasses the formation of geo-economic thinking at the level of theoretical and practical knowledge through the study of books, articles, scientific journals, and other literature that reflects the economic knowledge accumulated by society.

The second feature is related to the ways and means of organizing the formation of geo-economic thinking within society. On the one hand, it includes the formation of geo-economic thinking among the property-owning class, which constitutes the direct subject of geo-economics. On the other hand, it involves organized efforts aimed at improving geo-economic thinking among the country's population as a whole. These two features complement one another and represent two interrelated sides of a unified whole.

The main driving force of geo-economics is the class of owners. Therefore, the problem of forming geo-economic thinking within the property-owning class is regarded as one of the urgent tasks of strategic importance for the state.

In accordance with the material and spiritual trends of dialectical thinking, the geo-economic thinking of the property-owning class possesses ontological and epistemological foundations.

The ontological foundations of geo-economic thinking of the property-owning class consist of ^[6]:

- firstly, the existence of material and spiritual property, the possession of such property by the owner, and the enjoyment of its benefits by society in accordance with established norms;
- secondly, the quantity and quality of property accumulated in the hands of the owner;
- thirdly, the share of profit obtained from economic relations among owners, both within and beyond the state;
- fourthly, indicators reflecting the quality and quantity of constructed facilities, as well as technologies imported and implemented in production at the expense of the generated profit;
- fifthly, the actual existence of world markets for goods and the material value of trade turnover occurring within these markets.

The epistemological foundations of geo-economic thinking of the property-owning class consist of ^[6]:

- the economic thinking of the owner and its levels;
- the scientific potential of the owner;
- the skills, initiative, and entrepreneurial spirit of the owner;
- the owner's ability to comprehend the existing economic space;
- the spiritual world of the owner, and others.

As follows from the above, geo-economic thinking of the property-owning class is formed as a unity of objective and subjective dimensions, as well as ontological and epistemological components.

The main directions for the formation of geo-economic thinking among owners include the following ^[6].

1. The implementation of efforts aimed at creating a comprehensive understanding of the contemporary geo-economic picture of the world in the consciousness of the property-owning class.

The modern geo-economic picture includes, firstly, a general description of global economic spaces resulting from the mutual influence of national and transnational economic spaces; secondly, the interpretation of the global economic space in forms convenient for decision-making from the perspective of state strategies in international economic relations; thirdly, the division of global economic spaces into specific regions and levels; and, fourthly, the identification of spaces that generate shares of global income.

It follows that all of the above characteristics constitute the empirical foundation of geo-economic thinking, upon which logical reasoning, judgment, and evaluation within economic thinking are built.

2. The formation of geo-economic thinking through the development of scientific knowledge and comprehension of geo-economic space and time.

From this perspective, geo-economic space represents the localization of geo-economic attributes in a particular place, such as goods, barter, markets, profit, and income, while geo-economic time reflects the sequential relationships of these attributes within a defined temporal interval. Thus, geo-economics exists as a socio-economic phenomenon only within a specific time and space.

Only when the property-owning class possesses accurate knowledge of the contemporary geo-economic picture of the world, existing within geo-economic space and time, can it effectively generate profit and income through the sale of goods in the world market. This objective can be achieved solely through the development and application of geo-economic thinking.

Today, neither individual countries nor social groups and individuals are perceived as closed or self-sufficient entities. Instead, they are integrated into generalized systems of interrelation and interdependence.

Interrelation, interdependence, and interaction constitute natural, highly complex, and contradictory processes of globalization.

Globalization represents a universal and multilateral process of cultural, ideological, and economic integration among states, state associations, and national and ethnic communities, functioning as an inherent phenomenon of modern civilization.

Universal processes of globalization generate profound changes in rapprochement and cooperation among nations and states, followed by convergence and harmonization of living standards and their quality.

A key characteristic of globalization in the contemporary world is the extrapolation of liberal-democratic values across all regions without exception. As a result, political, economic, legal, and other systems become increasingly similar, while interdependence among countries reaches unprecedented levels. Never before have

peoples and cultures been so mutually dependent, as problems arising in one part of the world are instantaneously reflected across the global system.

The processes of globalization and homogenization contribute to the formation of a unified world community characterized by common norms, institutions, and cultural values, fostering a perception of the world as a single, interconnected space.

Globalization is characterized by several main aspects:

- internationalization, primarily expressed through expanding interrelations;
- liberalization, including the removal of trade barriers, increased mobility of investment, and the development of integration processes;
- westernization, reflected in the global dissemination of Western values and technologies;
- deterritorialization, resulting in transnational forms of activity and a reduction in the significance of state borders.

Globalization entails the formation of a unified international economic, legal, and cultural-information space, and its significance extends beyond purely economic frameworks, exerting a substantial influence on politics, ideology, and culture.

Although an integrated assessment of this phenomenon has not yet been fully articulated, it can be argued that globalization will play a decisive role in the world economy of the XXI century.

Globalization represents one of the few economic categories whose significance has extended beyond strictly professional discourse, with assessments occurring at both professional and everyday levels. Nevertheless, its objective nature remains beyond dispute.

A fundamental methodological position lies in recognizing the deep interconnection and interaction among the categories of globalization, geo-economy, internationalization of economic life, international economic cooperation, international economic relations, and the consequences arising from their interaction.

Globalization affects the economies of all countries, influencing the production of goods and services, labor utilization, investment flows, technological development, and the diffusion of technologies across national boundaries. These processes ultimately affect production efficiency, productivity, and competitiveness. It is precisely globalization that has intensified international competition. As a result, the phenomenon of geo-economics, along with associated geo-economic processes, has emerged within the global economic system.

Geo-economic processes in the world economy require each owner to quickly comprehend the logic of their development, to establish effective trade turnover relations, and to understand the dialectical interaction between geo-economics and the broader economic system. The logic underlying geo-economic development is realized through geo-economic thinking.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis shows that geo-economic thinking is a complex form of economic cognition shaped by globalization, economic space, and value transformations in modern society. It represents a dialectical unity of objective economic conditions and subjective intellectual activity, grounded in ontological and epistemological foundations. Geo-economic thinking enables economic actors, especially the property-owning class, to understand global economic processes, adapt to dynamic market conditions, and make strategic economic decisions. Therefore, it functions as an essential philosophical framework for interpreting contemporary geo-economic relations.

It is recommended to promote the development of geo-economic thinking through educational programs, economic policy-making, and scientific research. Particular emphasis should be placed on strengthening geo-economic competencies within the property-owning class. Furthermore, the integration of philosophical and economic approaches in geo-economic studies can enhance the effectiveness of regional development strategies and international economic cooperation in the context of globalization.

Literature:

1. Ponomarev, L. N., et al. *Economic Culture: The Nature and Trends of Development*. – Moscow: Mysl, 1987. – 55 p.
2. Valiev, B. *Economic Culture and Factors of Its Development*. – Tashkent: Publishing–Polygraphic Association “Tashkent Islamic University”, 2008. – 37 p.
3. Makhmudov, E. R. *World Economy: Contemporary Economic System*. – Tashkent: Umaid, 2004. – 528 p.
4. Ponomarev, L. N., et al. *Economic Culture: The Nature and Directions of Development*. – Moscow: Mysl, 1987. – 269 p.
5. Haydarov, F. *Laws Reform*. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2010. – 160 p.
6. Ubaydullaev, I. A. *Problems of Formation of Geo-Economic Thinking of Owners in the Context of Globalization // The Young Scientist*. – 2014. – No. 6. – pp. 873–875.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №12

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.